

Co-UDlabs

**Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research
Labs communities**

D8.5 – Report on use of designer soils for Sustainable Urban Drainage systems

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Background: about the Co-UDlabs Project

Co-UDlabs is an EU-funded project aiming to integrate research and innovation activities in the field of Urban Drainage Systems (UDS) to address pressing public health, flood risks and environmental challenges.

Bringing together 17 unique research facilities, Co-UDlabs offers training and free access to a wide range of high-level scientific instruments, smart monitoring technologies and digital water analysis tools for advancing knowledge and innovation in Urban drainage systems.

Co-UDlabs aims to create an urban drainage large-scale facilities network to provide opportunities for monitoring water quality, UDS performance and smart and open data approaches.

The main objective of the project is to provide a transnational multidisciplinary collaborative research infrastructure that will allow stakeholders, academic researchers, and innovators in the urban drainage water sector to come together, share ideas, co-produce project concepts and then benefit from access to top-class research infrastructures to develop, improve and demonstrate those concepts, thereby building a collaborative European Urban Drainage innovation community.

The initiative will facilitate the uptake of innovation in traditional buried pipe systems and newer green-blue infrastructure, with a focus on increasing the understanding of asset deterioration and improving system resilience.

Executive summary

This document is a Deliverable of the Co-UDlabs project, funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101008626.

This report compiles investigations conducted by AAU on a new modeling approach for designing techno-soils used in bioretention systems, as well as research from INSA Lyon on the filtration and retention capacities of a new engineered soil developed by the German company HAURATON. The performance of Hauraton's substrate was compared to that of natural soil.

In the context of growing urbanization, which exacerbates stormwater runoff and pollutant loading, this study aimed to assess whether this substrate could enhance water quality by retaining particulate and dissolved-phase pollutants. The investigation specifically focused on suspended solids, trace metals, and dissolved organic carbon (DOC).

Hydrodynamic and physical characterizations revealed that the HAURATON substrate has a texture like sandy loam, with low porosity but high hydraulic conductivity (0.322 mm/s), ensuring excellent drainage capacity. Despite technical challenges related to clogging, the HAURATON substrate demonstrated good retention capacity for certain trace metals such as cadmium, arsenic, and copper, along with effective DOC removal. However, its performance varied for other metals. It is important to note that these results were obtained under extreme and uncontrolled conditions—including stormwater derived from a settling basin heavily loaded with fine particles, absence of vegetation in the Hauraton reservoir, and a specific geometry differing from Hauraton's standard design—which likely limited performance and contributed to rapid clogging.

Nevertheless, the findings remain promising, particularly for the retention of dissolved pollutants. Future research will be conducted under more controlled conditions, exploring the use of the HAURATON substrate as an amendment or barrier layer in bioretention systems.

Regarding the modeling approach for technosoil design, the developed 1D model runs in MatLab ©. The hydrological component is based on the numerical Moving Mean Slope model (Moldrup et al., 1989), extended to incorporate evapotranspiration, while the chemical component relies on an analytical solution to the advection-convection-reaction equation for reactive chemical transport in unsaturated soils. Preliminary tests indicate that the proposed model successfully identifies filter medium design parameters capable of meeting both hydrological and chemical performance criteria, particularly when additional organic matter is incorporated into the top 50 cm of the existing subsoil layer. This work has resulted in a promising modeling platform for designer soils (filter media) in Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems (SUDS), which will be further tested and refined.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Context

In the current context, stormwater management proves to be a major issue. Indeed, soil sealing, linked to massive urbanization significantly increase runoff volumes of stormwater that can saturate urban drainage systems and lead to major flooding. This runoff water is also an important vector of pollutants from human activities, and the problems related to its management and treatment therefore constitute a significant threat to the quality of aquatic environments: groundwater can become contaminated and coastal ecosystems degraded.

Parallel to these environmental consequences, there are also health issues since the contamination of drinking water resources is a huge risk for public health. Furthermore, it is important to handle in a proper way the effects of climate change that tend to exacerbate the occurrence of extreme events such as exceptional rainfall and thus accentuate risks of pollution and flooding.

Hence, it is crucial to elaborate and implement SUDS to mitigate all these risks. The aim of this deliverable is therefore to emphasize the performances of two types of substrates in terms of retention and filtration of micropollutants present in runoff water, thus contributing to the broader objective of Co-UDlabs to develop effective stormwater management solutions adapted to the specificities of urban territories. In addition, an original model has been developed enabling to design techno-soils dedicated to treat runoff water in bioretention systems.

1.2. Objectives

As part of the Co-UDLabs project, this study sets the following objectives:

- Characterize the physical properties (particle size distribution, porosity) and hydrodynamic properties (hydraulic conductivity) of the HAURATON substrate to understand its functioning and identify potential limiting factors.
- Compare the filtration and retention performances of the HAURATON filtering substrate against those deriving from a natural soil.
- Establish an experimental protocol to evaluate the evolution of HAURATON substrate performance over time, taking into account, for example, the risks of clogging and pollutant release.
- Determine the key parameters influencing the effectiveness of the HAURATON substrate and propose recommendations for its optimal use
- Development of an innovative modelling approach to optimize the design of techno soils used as substrate in SUDS

2. MONITORING OF DESIGNER SOILS: MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Experimental prototypes

In order to compare the HAURATON substrate and natural soil performances, a specific prototype was installed at the OTHU DRB "Django-Reinhardt Basin" site in Chassieu, close to Lyon, France. Consisting of a retention-settling basin, it is located at the outlet of an industrial watershed and drained by a separate stormwater network. From

the network, water first enters a retention basin through an initial pipe before being evacuated through a second, regulated pipe into an infiltration basin (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Presentation of the DRB site.

The prototype consists in two small reservoirs containing each one Hauraton substrate and natural soil. They are supplied with a part of stormwater released from the detention basin (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Hauraton and natural soil substrates.

HAURATON company indicated a permeability for their substrate around 0.7 L/s/m^2 . The dimensions of the two reservoirs are $H=15 \text{ cm}$; $L = 40 \text{ cm}$ and $W = 32 \text{ cm}$. The flow rate to be considered according to the indication from Hauraton Company is therefore 0.09 L/s .

2.2. Physical and hydrodynamic characterizations

In collaboration with ENTPE Engineering School, INSA Lyon have also implemented infiltrometer tests and physical analysis to get the texture and the structure of the Hauraton substrate as well as its hydrodynamic characterization (hydraulic conductivity and initial water content prior to the irrigation with stormwater).

A Beerkan ring was placed and inserted a few centimeters into the Hauraton substrate. The filled infiltrometer was then placed above the ring before opening its piston, allowing pressure equilibrium between the latter and the water previously injected into the ring. A data logger connected to the infiltrometer recorded the data on an SD card until it was completely emptied.

This method has several major advantages. The automation of the process ensures reliable and rapid data collection while reducing the risk of human error. Moreover, it allows for directly obtaining the complete infiltration curve, enabling an analysis of the substrate's infiltration capacities.

Figure 3. Automated Infiltrometer tests.

2.3. Continuous monitoring

Continuous monitoring of the conductivity and turbidity was done at the inlet and outlet points of the small reservoir. After infiltration through 15 cm of soil - similar to the experimental conditions described by Garnier (2020) - the water from each small reservoir is collected in two small tanks connected to each small reservoir containing

natural soil in one of them and Hauraton substrate in another one. These two small tanks are equipped with a turbidimeter and a conductimeter. If required, samplings can be collected from each small tank.

The sensors used are:

- ISC 40 electrical conductivity probe [Yokogawa]: Measures electrical conductivity, correlated to the quantity of ions in water. Conductivity measures water's ability to conduct an electric current in relation to its ion load and the amount of dissolved mineral salts.
- CUS 41 turbidity probe [Endress+Hauser]: Evaluates water opacity due to suspended particles. Turbidity indicates the presence of suspended particles. The comparison between input and output turbidity values enables to assess the interception rate of suspended matter by Hauraton and natural soil substrates.
- Water level probe: estimates the water level in small tanks.

Turbidity measurements, for instance, can be significantly affected if sediment accumulates on the sensor, leading to artificially elevated readings. To mitigate this bias, regular sensor cleaning would be required to maintain accuracy between rainfall events. However, this approach is logistically challenging and labor-intensive in the context of this study.

2.4. Sampling and chemical analysis

In addition to continuous monitoring, water samples are collected during one of the 7 recorded rainfall events. They include raw stormwater as well as water filtered by the tested substrates, namely natural soil and aging and new HAURATON substrates:

- Raw stormwater from the detention basin
- Stormwater filtered by "natural soil" substrate
- Stormwater filtered by new "Hauraton" substrate
- Stormwater filtered by an "aging Hauraton" or "Old Hauraton" substrate (after 3 months of operation)

"Measurement blanks" are also performed to evaluate the potential chemicals released from the substrates. This method involves injecting distilled water and comparatively analyzing the output water from both prototypes (small reservoirs with natural soil and Hauraton substrate), comparing new and aging substrates. Samples are also sent to the laboratory to evaluate the potential release of trapped chemicals.

Laboratory analysis include particulate pollution analysis by ICP-MS to quantify trace metal elements (As, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Ni, Pb, Zn). This protocol offers high sensitivity and a wide dynamic range of concentrations.

This approach will provide a more detailed view of the substrates' reduction performance, although it is important to notice that this analytical protocol remains relatively expensive. This is why we have limited our research to trace metal elements.

3. MONITORING OF DESIGNER SOILS: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Physico-chemical and hydrodynamic characterization of the Hauraton substrate

The first step of our investigation was to determine the texture and grain size distribution of the Hauraton substrate. The natural soil properties were already investigated by Garnier (2020). The experimental results allowed to plot the particle size distribution curve of the substrate (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Particle size distribution of the substrate tested.

Table 1 indicates the percentages of silt, sand and clay distribution. Based on the texture triangle (Figure 5), the texture of the Hauraton substrate is similar to a loamy sand. Subsequently, it is necessary to identify the porosity of the material, that is, the proportion of void in the total volume, defined as follows : $\phi = V_{\text{void}} / V_{\text{total}}$. This involves identifying the importance of pores.

Table 1. Percentage of sand, silt and clay distribution

% Clay (0-0.002mm)	% Silt (0.002-0.05mm)	% Sand (0.05-2 mm)
~10%	~23%	~67%

Figure 5. Texture triangle

The experimental measurements yielded a substrate density of 1409.5 kg/m^3 , which is relatively close to that of muddy clay. The recorded water contents, based on two measurements are $w_1 = 7.6\%$ and $w_2 = 10.44\%$. These values are characteristic of compact sands and gravels. This also results in porosities of $\phi_1 = 10.72\%$ and $\phi_2 = 14.09\%$ for the two tests, which is relatively low compared to most natural soils whose porosity is between 30 and 60%. Indeed, the porosities obtained experimentally for the natural soil are $\phi_{1\text{Topsoil}} = 47.93\%$ and $\phi_{2\text{Topsoil}} = 53.35\%$.

The hydraulic conductivity was also assessed. It allows the evaluation of the substrate's capacity to let water passes through its structure. It is greatly influenced by the water content and porosity of the substrate. Using the BEST method (Lassabatere et al., 2006), the infiltration curve is plotted on Figure 6 and shows the evolution of this rate over time.

Figure 6. Infiltration curve of the Hauraton substrate.

The saturated hydraulic conductivity of the Hauraton substrate was measured at $K_s = 0.322 \text{ mm/s}$ (1159 mm/h). Although this is slightly lower than the manufacturer's reported value of 0.5 mm/s , the measured permeability remains within a consistent range. This discrepancy is likely attributable, at least in part, to differences in the measurement devices and methodologies used.

Despite this variation, the substrate exhibits a relatively high saturated hydraulic conductivity, indicating efficient drainage capacity. This value is also consistent with the results of the particle size analysis, as it aligns with the permeability typically observed in sandy-textured soils.

Furthermore, while the substrate demonstrates low porosity, it maintains good drainage efficiency. As demonstrated by Einsiedl (2018), fissured limestones are known to exhibit similar characteristics, where fractures facilitate water movement, leading to high hydraulic conductivity despite low porosity. The manufacturer's technical data sheet specifies a high carbonate content in the substrate. Given that limestone is a carbonate-rich sedimentary rock, the measured characteristics of the substrate align well with the properties reported by HAURATON.

3.2. Continuous monitoring based on conductivity and turbidity measurements

3.2.1. Variation of inflows supplying the prototypes

Turbidity and conductivity were monitored from October 26, 2024, to January 27, 2025. During this period, eleven rainfall events were identified based on data from the local weather station and peaks in the outlet flow rate from the detention basin (Figure 7). The data analysis focuses on these rainfall events. In order to illustrate the performances of the investigated substrate, rainfall events on Nov. 19 2025 (first event) and Jan. 25 2025 (last one) were selected.

Figure 7. Outlet flowrate from the detention basin - A fraction of this outlet flowrate is directed towards the prototypes

The recorded data include measurements of water turbidity and conductivity at the inlet and outlets of the prototypes. Water temperature, which ranged from 8 to 12°C during the study, was recorded but did not cause significant variations in conductivity within this thermal range.

3.2.2. Turbidity mitigation through prototypes

The initial analysis involved representing turbidity values at the inlet and outlet using box plots (Figures 8 and 9). This approach provides a visualization of the range of turbidity variations as water passes through the two substrates. Median comparison was preferred over mean comparison to minimize the influence of outliers, which could result from sensor measurement errors.

Figure 8. Boxplots of Turbidity variations during the first event on Nov. 19 2024

Figure 8 shows that the filtration process enables both prototypes to capture particulate matters, leading to a significant reduction in turbidity as water passes through the substrates. The highest turbidity peak can be attributed to the resuspension of particles in the detention basin, particularly at the beginning of the rainfall event (Zhu et al., 2020). The Hauraton substrate exhibits superior performance compared to the natural soil substrate. For the rainfall event on Nov. 19 2024, the natural soil substrate reduces turbidity by about 50%, while the HAURATON substrate demonstrates superior efficiency. Figure 9 indicates the variation of the turbidity during the rainfall event observed on January 25 2025.

Figure 9. Boxplots of Turbidity variations during the last event on Jan. 25 2025

The results presented in Figure 9 do not indicate a significant reduction in turbidity between the inlet and outlet. This can be attributed to the clogging process, which occurred after three months of operation, leading to overflow events. A portion of the overflow volume was redirected to the small tanks designed to collect filtered stormwater from the tested prototypes. This process likely explains the variability in turbidity values observed during the rainfall event.

3.2.3. Conductivity control through prototypes

The analysis of conductivity data during the first event (on Nov. 19 2024) reveals a slight increase as water passes through the substrate, a phenomenon typically attributed to the dissolution of minerals present in the filtering medium. The box plots displayed on Figure 10 confirm this trend, demonstrating that the increase remains moderate. This finding suggests that the substrates do not release excessive amounts of minerals into the filtered water.

Figure 10. Boxplots of Conductivity variations during the first event on Nov. 19 2024

The box plots displayed on Figure 11 show a significant decreasing of conductivity values during the second event. The aging of the substrate with the presence of organic matter, lead to effective retention of mineral salts. The presence of organic matter contributes to intercept some dissolved chemicals. Indeed, Spraakman and Drake (2021), cited in Shaves et al. (2024), also indicated that there is evidence that bioretention systems will continue to function well, from a hydrological perspective, for up to 10 years, given the age of the oldest site in this study, where 22 bioretention cells with different configurations were analyzed. This is likely due to the development of soil layer structure over time, from the deposition of organic matter, soil fauna activity, and environmental factors such as wetting and drying. We assume that similar mechanisms occurred in tested prototypes after 3 months of operation, with alternance between wetting and drying.

Figure 11. Boxplots of Conductivity variations during the last event on Jan. 25 2025

3.3. Discussion on continuous measurements

The exploitation of continuous monitoring data was hindered by several challenges. Firstly, fouling of the optical lenses in the turbidity sensors led to erroneous readings during certain rainfall events. Additionally, the HAURATON substrate experienced severe clogging, restricting water flow, despite its initially characterized high hydraulic conductivity. Although the geotextile was initially suspected as the cause, the issue was found to be intrinsic to the substrate, which hardened and became impermeable. The leading hypothesis attributes this to an excessive concentration of fine particles in the inlet water, causing rapid clogging due to exposure to highly polluted stormwater.

3.4. Sampling campaigns and chemical analysis

3.4.1. Particulate phase

Analysis of inlet and outlet water quality:

The analysis of water samples collected at the system's inlet and outlet enabled the calculation of reduction rates for various trace metals in both substrates. Figure 12 illustrates the ratio in percentage between outlet and inlet concentrations for each chemical. The raw data are summarized in a table in the appendix (Annex 1).

Figure 12. Ratio between outlet and inlet concentrations of metals

- Cadmium (Cd):** The HAURATON substrate exhibits excellent cadmium retention, with reduction rates exceeding 90% at the beginning of the experiment and maintaining at least 67% efficiency after several months of on-site operation (Figure 12). This performance remains superior to that of natural soil, suggesting that the substrate keeps its effectiveness over time, even under clogging conditions. However, it should be noted that the initial cadmium concentration in the inlet water is relatively low compared to other metal elements.
- Zinc (Zn) and Cobalt (Co):** The HAURATON substrate shows effectiveness in reducing Zinc and Cobalt, although natural soil demonstrates superior performance in both cases, even when the Hauraton substrate is new.

- **Chromium (Cr) and Zirconium (Zr):** Similar trends were observed for chromium and zirconium, with the HAURATON substrate showing moderate reduction rates. However, its performance remained lower than that of natural soil. Additionally, in the case of zirconium, the reduction efficiency declined over time, correlating with the progressive clogging of the substrate.
- **Nickel (Ni) and Lead (Pb):** The HAURATON substrate, in its initial state, exhibits effective reduction of nickel and lead, outperforming natural soil. However, under clogging conditions, overflow events occur supplying the collection tank and the release of these elements is observed at the outlet, indicating a limited long-term retention capacity for these metal traces.
- **Arsenic (As):** A relatively low reduction of Arsenic is observed, both for new and used substrates.
- **Copper (Cu):** A particular result is observed for copper, with higher reduction for the aging Hauraton substrate compared to natural soil.

Analysis of blank samples:

The analysis of blank samples was also conducted.

Figure 13. Ratio between outlet and inlet concentrations of metals for blank samples

- **Copper (Cu):** The HAURATON substrate exhibits a significant release of copper when newly installed, with outlet concentrations comparable to those in the outlet point of the detention basin (basin inlet on Figure 13). Similarly, the aged substrate continues to release copper, suggesting that this phenomenon occurs independently of the substrate's usage state. This observation challenges the hypothesis of an initial leaching effect. The previously observed reduction under aged conditions may instead be attributed to the accumulation of organic matter on the surface of the prototypes. Copper is known for its strong affinity for organic compounds and predominantly accumulates in the upper soil horizon, which is rich in organic matter (Garnier, 2020).
- **Arsenic (As) and Chromium (Cr):** Small quantities of Arsenic and Chromium are naturally released during measurement blanks, whether the substrate is new or used. The decrease in reduction with substrate age could be explained by a reduced trapping capacity due to wear.

- **Cobalt (Co), Nickel (Ni), and Zinc (Zn):** The new substrate naturally presents small concentrations of Cobalt, Nickel, and Zinc at the outlet compared to basin water (Figure 13). The used substrate shows much higher concentrations after blanks analysis, explaining the observed release for Nickel and the slow reduction rate for Zinc.
- **Lead (Pb):** Although there is no natural release of Lead in the new state, a release is observed with the used substrate.
- **Cadmium (Cd):** As already mentioned, the substrate is truly effective in trapping Cadmium, as negligible quantities are released after blank samples analysis of both new and used substrates.

Overall, the HAURATON substrate exhibits lower efficiency than topsoil in retaining particulate pollutants, with reduced removal rates in most cases. Its performance tends to decline over time due to clogging, increasing the risk of releasing previously retained contaminants.

However, notable exceptions include Cadmium, for which the substrate demonstrates highly effective and sustained retention, as well as Arsenic, which, despite relatively low removal rates, is better retained than with natural soil. Additionally, Copper retention appears promising in the presence of organic matter, suggesting a potential role of organic interactions in its sequestration.

3.4.2. Dissolved phase

Figure 14 shows the concentrations of dissolved organic carbon. The HAURATON substrate exhibits a significant capacity for reducing DOC, outperforming natural soil, which tends to release it. This efficiency is particularly pronounced when the substrate is new, showing a higher reduction rate compared to the aged substrate.

Figure 14. Dissolved organic carbon (DOC) concentrations at the inlet and outlet of substrates

However, this finding raises concerns regarding the long-term behavior of the substrate. Analyses indicate an elevated DOC concentrations in the blank samples of the aged substrate, suggesting a potential release of accumulated pollutants over time. This phenomenon mirrors observations made for certain particulate metals, indicating a similar trend for dissolved contaminants.

Despite these considerations, the HAURATON substrate appears to be a promising alternative to natural soil for the retention of dissolved pollutants. As already observed by Garnier (2020), these results align with previously documented performances of bioswale.

Nonetheless, as highlighted by Huang et al. (2025), the absence of vegetation warrants caution in interpreting these findings, as plants are known to play a crucial role in the mitigation of dissolved pollution. This underscores the necessity of further investigations incorporating vegetation to provide a more comprehensive and representative assessment of the HAURATON substrate's performance under real-life conditions.

4. MODELLING APPROACH : The LAZE model tool for designing technosoils

4.1. Design criteria

University of Aalborg has developed a preliminary version of a user-friendly model for design of a filter soil under a basin for local area infiltration, LAI, or soil-based sustainable urban drainage systems, SUDS. The model is called Local-Area-Zero-Emission (LAZE). The assumed above-soil and below-soil systems and processes are illustrated in Fig 15.

Figure 15. The above (a) and below (b) soil compartments and processes considered in the LAZE filter medium design model.

The LAZE model is 1D and runs in MatLab. The water part of the LAZE design model is the numerical Moving Mean Slope model (Moldrup et al., 1989) extended with evapotranspiration, and the chemical part of the model is an analytical solution to the advection-convection-reaction equation for reactive chemical transport in unsaturated soil. The main design criteria are:

1. sufficient water infiltration to avoid flooding above basin level, and
2. sufficient residence time and retardation of selected environmental impact chemicals.

Criteria 1 and 2 are counterintuitive and counteracting, since criterion 1 assumes rapid water transport and high filter medium permeability and criterion 2 assumes slow water transport and high residence time. Therefore, the model finds - if possible - the optimal set of filter media parameters where both criteria are fulfilled. Inputs to the LAZE model are:

1. filter media and subsoil particle size distribution (clay, silt, fine and coarse sand according to ISSS standards, assumed or measured for a filter media candidate by dry sieving using a sieving tower),
2. filter media and subsoil compaction level defined by dry bulk density (assumed or measured on intact soil samples if an already existing subsoil layer is also considered a filter media candidate),
3. filter media and subsoil depth
4. filter medium and subsoil water retention properties (water content at pF 2 and pF 4.2, predicted by pedotransfer function based on particle size distribution and compaction or measured on intact soil samples if an already existing original subsoil layer is also considered a filter medium candidate)
5. filter medium and subsoil saturated hydraulic conductivity (predicted by pedotransfer function based on particle size distribution and compaction, e.g. the Nielsen et al. 2018 model, or measured on intact soil samples or in-situ using e.g. double-ring infiltrometer if an already existing subsoil layer is also considered a filter medium candidate)
6. basin size
7. in case of hydrophobic organic chemicals like PAHs, the filter media organic matter content (assumed or measured for a filter media candidate by loss of ignition in ignition oven)
8. selected precipitation time series

4.2. Concept Overview - Calculation and Design

The first step is to define basin dimensions, filter soil layer height, and the fundamental texture and compaction properties for the technosoil (filter soil) layer. Soil properties input include the contents (%) of clay, silt, fine sand, coarse sand, and organic matter, and the soil dry bulk density (g/cm^3). The model now uses pedotransfer functions to evaluate the soil hydraulic curves and chemical parameters that determine the water flow and chemical transport and retardation (delay).

For water flow, this include the soil-water retention curve (relation between soil-water matric potential and volumetric soil-water content) and the saturated-unsaturated hydraulic conductivity curve (relation between soil hydraulic conductivity and soil-water content), based on the well-known Campbell (1974)

functions, and with the three main input parameters from the pedotransfer functions being air-entry soil-water matric potential (Ψ_e , equal to saturated capillary rise in cm of water), the Campbell pore-size distribution index (b), and the saturated hydraulic conductivity (K_{sat}).

For chemical transport and delay, this includes the scaled chemical dispersivity (τ , ratio of chemical dispersion coefficient to pore-water velocity), using the Gelhar et al. (1992) model for length scaling, and the linear adsorption coefficient (K_d ; cm^3/g).

Based on the model calculation of basin dimensions and chemical breakthrough curves, it is evaluated if the twin criteria of sufficient infiltration/storage of water and sufficient delay and retainment of chemicals are met.

If not, the concept then allows for an iterative process of changing input basin dimensions and technosoil properties (basin dimensions, height of filter soil layer and its mineral texture, organic matter content, and compaction) until both criteria - if possible - are met for the given water input and the selected chemicals. The iterative design set-up simultaneously considering water and chemical behavior is unique for SUDS design.

Output from the model includes hydrographs over needed water depth in basin over time during a defined time series of precipitation and 5%, 50%, and 90% chemical breakthrough time at the bottom of the filter medium layer and one meter below the bottom of the filter medium layer (i.e. in the original subsoil). For initial test and implementation, a fine sandy location at St. Restrup Common in the vicinity of Aalborg was considered, where a soil-based SUDS system for a planned residential area is under actual design. Loose and intact soil samples were taken in the existing subsoil layer. The LAZE model found filter medium design parameters that could fulfil both design criteria (for water and selected chemicals). If additional organic matter was added (mixed-in the top 50 cm) to the existing subsoil layer at St. Restrup Common. Thus, a promising model platform for designer soils (filter media) for SUDS systems has been made and will be further tested and improved. Examples of model output are shown in Fig 16.

Figure 16. Example of the LAZE model output for 34 years of historical rainfall. (a) Required basin water level as function of time, and (b) chemical breakthrough curves for water and selected PFAS compounds at bottom of the filter layer.

5. Conclusion and perspectives

In conclusion, this study on the effectiveness of the HAURATON substrate in treating runoff water reveals promising results, with some limitations. The hydraulic conductivity of the Hauraton substrate enables a very good infiltration capacities. Continuous monitoring demonstrated reductions in terms of conductivity and turbidity. This result is consistent with chemical analyses that revealed good retention of dissolved pollution.

However, the substrate was less effective for retaining particulate pollution due to rapid clogging process. Despite this, good removal efficiencies were observed for Cadmium, Arsenic, and Copper. The aging of the substrate over the time led to a decrease in its performance, with a risk of partial leaching processes. These observations highlight the importance of regular maintenance and potentially periodic replacement of the substrate to maintain its optimal performances.

It should be noted, however, that these performances in certain areas were observed despite the raw and extreme experimental conditions we chose for this study. On one hand, the absence of vegetation, with a single compacted layer and a high inlet concentration of fine particles, indeed highlighted the substrate's sensitivity to clogging, which limits its long-term effectiveness.

Promising applications exist for the HAURATON substrate. This substrate can be used as an amendment to topsoil or as a barrier layer optimizing stormwater treatment systems, particularly thanks to its effectiveness in reducing dissolved pollution.

Regarding the modelling approach, the LAZE model demonstrated its capabilities to properly design technosoils with promising preliminary results. Thanks to Co-Udlabs context of collaborations, LAZE approach will be applied to optimize the design of the Hauraton substrate. This next step will strengthen AAU and INSA collaboration, involving also all motivated partners.

6. References

Anuj, Kulshreshtha., Palanisamy, Shanmugam. (2016). Estimation of turbidity in coastal waters using satellite data

Chaves, M.T.R., Farias, T.R.L., & Eloi, W.M. (2024). Comparative analysis of bioretention design strategies for urban runoff infiltration: A critical overview. *Ecological Engineering*, 207, 107352.

Chocat. (1997). Le rôle possible de l'urbanisation dans l'aggravation du risque d'inondation : l'exemple de l'Yseron à Lyon / The potential role of urbanization in increasing the risk of flooding : the example of the Yzeron in Lyon. *Géocarrefour*, 72(4), 273-280

Davis, A.P. (2008). Field performance of bioretention: hydrology impacts. *Journal of Hydrologic Engineering*, 13(2), 90-95

Einsiedl, Florian. "Conceptualization of flow and transport in a limestone aquifer by combining isotopic and hydrochemical tracers with hydrogeological methods." *Journal of Hydrology*, vol. 561, 2018, pp. 31-43.

Gelhar, L. W., Welty, C., & Rehfeldt, K. R. (1992). A critical review of data on field-scale dispersion in aquifers. *Water Resources Research*, 28(7), 1955-1974.

Huang, T., Sage, J., Técher, D., & Gromaire, M.-C. (2025). Hydrological performance of bioretention in field experiments and models: A review from the perspective of design characteristics and local contexts. *Science of the Total Environment*, 965, 178684.

Lassabatère, L., Angulo-Jaramillo, R., Soria Ugalde, J. M., Cuenca, R., Braud, I., & Haverkamp, R. (2006). Beerkan estimation of soil transfer parameters through infiltration experiments—BEST. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 70(2), 521-532.

Marshal, Soni. (2017). Variation of conductivity of the different sources of water with temperature and concentration of electrolyte solution NaCl. *The Pharma Innovation Journal*

Moldrup, P., Rolston, D. E., & Hansen, J. A. (1989). Rapid and numerically stable simulation of one-dimensional, transient water flow in unsaturated, layered soils. *Soil Science*, 148(3), 219-226.

Nielsen, J. E., Karup, D., De Jonge, L. W., Ahm, M., Bentzen, T. R., Rasmussen, M. R., & Moldrup, P. (2018). Can the volume ratio of coarse to fine particles explain the hydraulic properties of sandy soil? *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 82(5), 1093-1100.

Parra., Ali, Ahmad., Sandra, Sendra., Jaime, Lloret., Pascal, Lorenz. (2024). Combination of Machine Learning and RGB Sensors to Quantify and Classify Water Turbidity.

Qiao, Y. (2015). Caractérisation et évolution de la qualité des eaux de ruissellement de toiture selon leur usage (récupération, rétention)

R.G., Jones. (2002). Measurements of the electrical conductivity of water.

Robin Garnier. (2020) Systèmes alternatifs de gestion des eaux pluviales : Contribution à l'analyse de performances conjointes en matière d'hydrologie quantitative et de piégeage de micropolluants. Comparaison systèmes à la source – système centralisé. Ingénierie de l'environnement. Université de Lyon, 2020.

Ryad Bouzoudja (2015) Fonctionnement hydrique d'un Technosol superficiel - application à une toiture végétalisée

Seitz et al., (2020) Electrolytic conductivity at pure water level. *Metrologia*

Spraakman, S., Drake, J.A.P., 2021. Hydrologic and soil properties of mature bioretention cells in Ontario, Canada. *Water Sci. Technol.* 84 (12), 3541–3560. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2021.464>

Zhu, X., Chatain, V., Gautier, M., Blanc-Biscarat, D., Delolme, C., Dumont, N., Aubin, J.-B., Lipeme Kouyi, G. (2020). Combination of Lagrangian Discrete Phase Model and sediment physico-chemical characteristics for the prediction of the distribution of trace metal contamination in a stormwater detention basin. *Science of The Total Environment*, 698, 134263. Open Access. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.134263>

Annex 1. Table with values on reduction ratio of particulate pollutants

Analysis of inlet and outlet water quality

Element	Basin Water [µg/L]	Soil Outlet [µg/L]	Soil Reduction [%]	Hauraton Outlet [µg/L]	Old Hauraton Reduction [%]	New Hauraton [µg/L]	New Hauraton Reduction [%]
As	0.385	1.42	overflow	0.361	6.23	0.349	9.35
Cd	0.081	0.045	44.44	<LQ	>67.9	<LD	90.12
Co	1.02	0.134	86.86	0.621	39.12	0.3	70.59
Cr	0.358	0.245	31.56	0.309	13.69	0.264	26.26
Cu	4.89	4.79	2.04	4.34	11.25	9.82	Overflow
Ni	20.8	15.5	25.48	29.6	Recharge	10.6	49.04
Pb	0.199	0.989	Overflow	0.223	Overflow	0.122	38.69
Zn	243	28	88.48	88	63.79	20.7	91.48

Analysis of blank samples:

Element	Basin Water [µg/L]	Soil Outlet [µg/L]	New Hauraton Outlet [µg/L]	Old Hauraton Outlet [µg/L]
As	0.385	1.19	0.586	0.517
Cd	0.081	<LQ	0.038	<LQ
Co	1.02	<LQ	0.176	0.4
Cr	0.358	0.234	0.324	0.308
Cu	4.89	3.28	4.31	4.06
Ni	20.8	14.7	1.77	31.1
Pb	0.199	0.541	<LQ	0.218
Zn	243	34.8	3.6	91

Annex 2. Table of concentrations of dissolved pollutants

Analysis of outlet water quality:

Parameter	Clean Soil [mg/L]	Clean Old Hauraton [mg/L]	Clean New Hauraton [mg/L]
TIC	17.3	19.7	42.9
TC	26.5	27.6	48.9
DOC	9.2	7.9	6

Analysis of blank samples:

Parameter	Basin Water [mg/L]	Soil [mg/L]	Old Hauraton [mg/L]	New Hauraton [mg/L]
DOC	8.9	10.8	7.8	7.1